

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Based on the requirements of the globalization period, the teacher should master innovative technologies in order to comprehensively improve the personality of the student in the educational process, the result of the innovative process in education, to rise to the level of technology.*

Keywords: *innovative process, global thinking, raising children, independence, inquisitiveness, creativity, interactive teaching method.*

Introduction

Based on the requirements of today's globalization period, special attention is paid to the comprehensive improvement of the student's personality, development of cognitive activity, as well as the formation of global thinking in the educational process. If the goal of each country is to take its place on the stage of history and join the ranks of civilized countries, then the main achievements of economically developed countries depend on the ability to use the wealth on the ground, not on the abundance or size of underground resources. In order to meet this need, paying attention to quality, conscious education of today's young generation is a big problem of today.

Research materials and methodology. If we remember the famous words of Ulug Abai: "Time makes a person mature, whoever is bad, all his contemporaries are guilty", now our country is rising, and our spiritual values and national development have started to develop towards world civilization. In the modern school, a huge amount of pedagogical experience has been accumulated, which can be used in real pedagogical activities, but not all of them are used in the same way, because many teachers and leaders do not need to learn and use this experience. nor do they have the skills and qualifications to analyze these experiences. Teachers, like their colleagues, do not pay attention to the need to analyze their pedagogical experience. In this direction, teachers are expected to turn to innovative educational development. In general, two important problems of pedagogy are the basis of innovative educational development:

- the problem of teaching pedagogical experience;
- the problem of implementing the achievements of the science of psychology and pedagogy into practice.

The result of the innovative process in education is the use of innovations that appear at the intersection of theory and practice, both theoretically and practically. One of the main goals of the new technology is to educate the child, form his freedom, activity, and make independent decisions. Use of innovative technologies is a necessity of life. We all know that the main task of modern science teachers is to direct education to the result, that is, to master innovative new

technology. Introducing innovative approaches to the educational process in accordance with the new needs of society requires the teacher's incessant inquisitiveness and creativity. In this regard, it is necessary to strive to master modern innovative technology that educates each student according to his abilities, educates him to be independent, inquisitive, and creative. Because the organization of the educational process on the basis of the state educational standard requires the introduction of new pedagogical technologies and innovative control and measurement tools in the monitoring of students' knowledge. The new pedagogical technology of teaching is aimed at the humanization of teaching, the formation of a competent, all-round person who can develop and educate himself, using modern trends. Along with improving the quality of students' professional education, it allows them to see their own potential, develop themselves, and look critically at themselves. Increases cognitive activity and develops creativity. It opens an effective and clear way for the teacher to study the person, to know him in all aspects, to achieve the goal of education. Scientists and teachers are looking for ways to develop cognitive activity to meet the requirements of the educational system. I.P. Pavlov said "...with a good method, a talentless person does a lot of work, and with a bad method, even a great person works in vain."

Therefore, while assessing the role of certain methods in the education and development of a person, it is necessary to say that at each stage of development, research and proposals on the use of methods that can "penetrate the deep source" of human consciousness should be taken into account the relevance of society today. In the current education system of our country, the most important task is to bring the level of knowledge of the young generation to the international level by switching to the national education module. According to the requirements of the times, it is not enough to be a science teacher, a teacher should be a moderator, innovator, and technologist.

Search results. In order to be promoted to the level of inn technician, the teacher must master innovative technologies, and then learn which subject to use in science effectively. That is, each innovative technology is studied, then the acquired technologies are approved (applied during the lesson), the teacher analyzes and selects the technology according to the topic. The teacher should be able to effectively use the elements of technology, taking into account the age characteristics of the student's natural talent and ability. Innovation is the first practical application of a new idea, even if it originated in science rather than in a laboratory. Innovations are aimed at institutions, organizations, local, regional and state institutions. The word innovation is translated from Latin and means to introduce something new. Innovation is not just any innovation or novelty; it is a process that improves the efficiency of the existing knowledge system. Innovative activity is the measures and the process itself that ensure the innovative process at any level of education. Pedagogical innovations are related to the reconstruction, improvement, change of the educational system, or the creation of some of its properties and aspects (new legislation, structures, concepts and integration relations, etc.). The innovation process includes the purpose, structure, tasks, technology and human resources of the organization. Technological innovations are modern computer and telecommunication technologies. Technological innovations make a great contribution to the fundamental change of economic mechanisms, the organization of the work of teachers and students, and the character of teaching activities.

Modern teaching technologies have the following requirements: clearly defining the purpose of education, its scientific justification, with high-quality results of activity; to have the ability to fully accept the educational material; free communication during the educational process; to have the ability to constantly improve and supplement it. One of the main innovative methods

is the "interactive educational method". The main principle is the formation and development of personality through pedagogical communication and communication dialogue. Interactive method - frequent use of methods, changing its capabilities in each lesson - is the main task of the teaching team. Interactive educational technology (IET) is an educational activity of a teacher and a student, which can create a situation of mutual success in motivational, intellectual, emotional and other aspects during educational activities, for students guarantees the creation of pedagogically effective cognitive relationships. Interactive methods include: ♦ method of brainstorming; ♦ work in a group; ♦ problematic composition methods; ♦ role-playing games; reading; ♦ business games; ♦ critical thinking method; ♦ discussions etc. b. The main functions of innovative activity include changing the components of the pedagogical process: goals, educational content, educational form, methods, approaches, technologies, management system, etc. At the same time, all researchers should not consider innovation as the pursuit of innovation in itself, because innovation is a purposeful, conscious change.

Discussions.

Today, innovative changes are taking place in various directions, forming a new content of education; processing and introduction of new technologies of education; use methods and methods of learning a new program; creating conditions for students to determine their own destiny during the educational process; change of thinking style, interaction between teacher and student, creation and development of creative and innovative team in educational institutions. In all the contradictions, costs and disadvantages of these processes, they give a positive character. This innovation makes it possible to eliminate the burden inherent in education as a social institution, to create a mechanism for quick and flexible response to changes in the social system, state and individual needs, which are considered urgent tasks today, and to create conditions for the development of local education. So, the common aspect of the methods of understanding the essence of pedagogical innovation considered above is that their main focus is on the process and result of pedagogical creativity. All researchers emphasize the need to provide a new theoretical analysis and understanding of the essence of educational innovation processes, to ensure continuous innovative action. This need, in turn, raises the issue of training special specialists, including qualified teachers in the field of pedagogical innovations. The success of the development of innovative education is determined by the preparation of teachers for innovative activities and continuous innovation. An important component of this training includes the ability to be flexible and proactive in updating society, the labor market, the individual, technologies, and the continuous information environment in one's professional activities. Thus, the teacher's qualification is one of the important conditions for the stability of the development of innovations in education. Therefore, targeted development of professional competencies of pedagogues is an important factor of innovative development of education.

Conclusion

In order for teachers to improve their qualifications and not switch to traditional teaching methods after being involved in practice, it is important to systematically implement methodological support and to act in cooperation at the school, district, city, region, republic level. is important. Today, network communities, mutual exchange of experience in various forms, publications promoting common ideas, popularization of work experience on the online platform are systematically implemented. This, in turn, is a favorable factor for the teacher's professional support, development and professional development.

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